

STUDY OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The study was undertaken to examine the Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. The sample of the study comprised of 160 secondary school students (80 boys and 80 girls) of class 10th grade selected randomly from various secondary schools of Jamshedpur city of East Singhbhum district. The study was done on the basis of locality, management and gender. The data was analysed with the help of mean, standard deviation, t- test and correlation. The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of the secondary school students. The study further reveals that there is no significant difference between boys and girls with respect to emotional intelligence and also their academic achievement. Whereas it is found that there is a significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students in the aspects of emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Also there is a significant difference found between private and government secondary school students in respect to both emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Academic Achievement, Secondary School Students

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important tool for everyone to succeed in life and get something different and helps a lot in lessening the challenges of difficult life. Knowledge gained throughout the education period enables each and every individual to be confident about their life; it opens various doors to the opportunities of achieving better prospects in life. In such a competitive world, it is must for all to have good education. Educational Psychology is one of the many

branches of Psychology dealing mainly with the problems, processes and products of education. In other words, educational Psychology may be defined as the branch of psychology which studies the behaviour of the learner in relation to his/her educational needs and environment. In this context, the emotion plays quiet a significant role in providing directions to behaviour and thus shaping the personality according to their development. Crow & Crow (1973) has defined emotions as “Emotion is an affective experience that accompanies generalized inner adjustment and mental and psychological stirred-up states in the individual and that show itself in his overt behaviour”. The ability to control the emotions has become important for the students as not to be carried away by the flow of negative and evil elements which may create a hindrance in the academic performance of the students. The management of emotions has given rise to the most talked term “Emotional Intelligence”. Lam and Kirby (2002) are of the opinion that Emotional Intelligence involves perceiving, understanding and regulating emotions. Kanoy (2011) says - Emotional Intelligence helps people to solve real world problems, manage stress and in decision making, etc., and it acts as an indicator of an individual's social interaction. From the above definition is clear that Emotional Intelligence is the ability to identify, assess and control the emotions of oneself, of others and of group. There are five elements identified as the components of emotional intelligence: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills that comprise the field of emotional intelligence. High Emotional intelligence is thought to be a protective factor for mental and physical health (Parker et al., 2001).

In the present world academic achievement is given utmost important for students. Academic achievement has become an index of a child's future in the highly competitive world. Adeyemo (2001) opined that the major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic achievements by students. To bring the pupil in certainty of successful academic achievements it is highly important to develop their personality with emotional intelligence. (Goleman 1995; Elias Ubriaco, Reese et al ., 1992, Svetlana, 2007) have found that high emotional intelligence can contribute to a

student in the learning process. Finnegan (1998) argued that school should help students learn the abilities underlying the emotional intelligence. There has been also seen a close relationship between the emotional intelligence and the academic achievement of the students. Fatima et. al. (2011) conducted a research which indicated a positive and significant relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Svetlana (2007) suggests the need to incorporate emotional intelligence training into Secondary education curricula, due to a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. The findings of the research may also support the need to incorporate emotional intelligence curriculum into college academic programs.

From the above discussion it can be highly assumed that there is a significant relationship between the emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Previously emotional intelligence did not gain much importance in education but with the advent of educational psychology now emotional intelligence has become an integral part of the education. In order to assess the relationship of emotional intelligence and academic achievements of Jharkhand students, where not much of the studies have been reported since the advent of the course, it was very enthusiastically intended to take up this study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Study of Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students.
2. To study the significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to gender.
3. To study the significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to

- gender
4. To study the significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to locality.
 5. To study the significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to locality.
 6. To study the significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to management.
 7. To study the significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to management.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- H_{0.1}:** There is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students.
- H_{0.2}:** There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to gender.
- H_{0.3}:** There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender
- H_{0.4}:** There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to locality.
- H_{0.5}:** There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to locality.
- H_{0.6}:** There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to management.
- H_{0.7}:** There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to management.

METHODOLOGY

For investigation and collection of the data descriptive survey method was used to find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement and to find out any significant difference between the mean scores of urban/rural, private/government, girls/boys students in relation to emotional intelligence and their academic achievement.

SAMPLE

In the present study, the sample consisted of 160 Secondary School students of Jamshedpur city, East Singhbhum district. For this purpose random sampling was used. Emotional Intelligence Scale as well as Academic Achievement Test was developed by the researcher which had close ended questions with a proper score card which made the research work more at ease.

Table -1: Name and Number of Urban Secondary Schools from where data was collected

Sl. No	Name of the School	Class Selected	No. of Students	
1.	Amar Jyoti School	X	10 boys	10 girls
2.	Kabir Memorial High School	X	10 boys	10 girls
3.	Sri DevasthanHansrajGoyal School	X	10 boys	10 girls
4.	People's Academy High School	X	10 boys	10 girls

Table -2: Name and Number of Rural Secondary Schools from where data was collected

Sl. No	Name of the School	Class Selected	No. of Students	
1.	Blue Bells English High School	X	10 boys	10 girls
2.	UtkramitUchchVidyalaya	X	10 boys	10 girls
3.	St. Robert School	X	10 boys	10 girls
4.	Birsa Memorial High School	X	10 boys	10 girls

ADMINISTRATION OF THE TOOLS

In the beginning the questionnaire of Academic Achievement and Emotional Intelligence scale was provided randomly to 10 boys and 10 girls of X from each of the 8 selected schools randomly. For the Academic Achievement scale four options were given for each of the question. Emotional Intelligence scale had 35 questions and for each question, numbers were given 1-5 and the students had to circle the number to which was appropriate to them. The responses of the students were collected and used for the further calculations.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

$H_{0.1}$: There is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students.

The framed hypotheses of the study has been analysed and the results has been presented below.

Table 3: Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students.

Variable of Study	N	r	Sig
Emotional Intelligence	160	0.186	Significant
Academic Achievement	160		

The collected data has been analysed using coefficient of correlation technique and the result are presented in table-3.

The obtained coefficient 'r' value between the emotional intelligence and academic achievement is 0.186 . The correlation value shows that the obtained value is significant and there is a positive relation between the two. The positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement is seen as the student's academic performance is better when they are emotionally intelligent.

The previous study conducted by Fatima et. al (2011) also shows that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement whereas the study conducted by Mohzan et. al (2013) shows that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Various studies have found positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement and have suggested that there should be a focus on the emotional intelligence also as the academic achievement is effected by the emotional intelligence of the secondary school students. A student when emotionally stable has wider prospects for academic achievement and this forms the base by which the present study is to be imparted.

The above results has been also shown through figure 1.

Figure 1 : Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students.

$H_{0.2}$: There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to gender.

To test the above hypothesis the t-ratio test has been done and presented below in table - 4.

Table 4: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of emotional intelligence of boys and girls.

Gender	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Boys N=80	123.81	14.67	1.030*
Girls N=80	121.12	18.16	

*Not Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 1.030 is less than that of the table t- value 1.97 for 158 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. The difference is considered to be not statistically significant which clearly indicates that there exists no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of secondary school girls and boys.

There has been an assumption that the boys are more emotionally intelligent than the girls as they know very well to handle the situations without being getting effected by their emotions. But this study proves it that the secondary school girls are equally emotionally intelligent and is capable of understanding their emotions with others, handling relations, controlling emotion in various situations. This is mainly because the girls are being brought out from their comfort zone and now they are getting exposure or experience to various situations which are making them emotionally strong.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of Oommen (2014) where the study found that there is no significant difference between secondary school boys and secondary schools girls in respect to emotional intelligence. In contrast to this the study conducted by Nadeem (2016) shows that there is a significant difference between secondary school boys and secondary school girls in respect to emotional intelligence where boys showed greater emotional intelligence than girls.

This study has thus reflected that there is no difference in the emotional intelligence of boys and girls which may be because of provision of equal opportunities to both the sexes.

The obtained finding has been presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Emotional Intelligence of Male and Female

$H_{0,3}$: There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender.

The obtained data were analysed and presented below in table-5.

Table 5: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of academic achievement of boys and girls.

Gender	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Boys N=80	14.63	3.76	0.53*
Girls N=80	14.27	4.77	

*Not Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 0.53 is less than that of the table t- value 1.97 for degree of freedom df (158) at 0.05 level of significance. The difference is considered to be not statistically significant which clearly indicates that there exists no significant difference between the secondary school boys and secondary school girls with respect to their academic achievement.

There has always been a debate over the issue as who has more of the academic achievement, the boys or the girls. But this study makes it quite clear that there is no difference between the secondary school

girls and secondary school boys in respect to academics. From a very long time there were only the boys who were the achievers in academics over the girls. But today the scenario has changed and the girls have equal opportunities for education and even the girls have become competitive and want to excel in their performances. Today the girls are getting equally what the boys are getting and there is no discrimination made between the boys and the girls in any aspect may be of education or career.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of Oommen (2016) where the study found that there is no significant difference between secondary school boys and secondary schools girls in respect to their academic achievement. The academic achievement of both the boys and girls were found to be similar. The finding has been also represented in fig - 3.

Figure 3:- Academic Achievement of Boys and Girls

H_{0.4}: There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to locality.

For testing of the above hypothesis data analyses has been done using t - ratio test and the results has been presented in table - 6.

Table 6: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of emotional intelligence of rural and urban secondary school students.

Locality	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Rural N=80	119.26	17.56	2.49*
Urban N=80	125.67	14.81	

*Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 2.49 is greater than that of the table t- value 1.97 for degree of freedom df (158) at 0.05 level of significance. The difference is considered to be statistically significant which states that there exists a significant difference between urban secondary school students and rural secondary school students. The study shows that the secondary school students of urban area are more emotionally intelligent than that of the secondary school students of rural area. This may be because the urban area schools involve emotional development of the students where as the rural area schools do not focus on the emotional development of the students.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of Sinha & Suman (2013) where the study found that there is a significant difference between urban secondary school students and rural secondary schools students in respect to emotional intelligence, the urban secondary school students were found to be more emotionally intelligent than the rural secondary school students. But in contrast to this the study conducted by Subramanyam & Rao (2008) found that there is no significant difference between urban and rural secondary school students in respect to locality. The finding of the present study reflects that urban background students are emotionally more stronger due to more focus on the activities promoting emotional intelligence in these schools. The findings has been also presented in fig. 4.

Figure 4:- Emotional Intelligence of Rural and Urban Secondary School Students

$H_{0.5}$: There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to locality.

The hypothesis has been tested applying appropriate statistical device and the results obtained has been presented in table - 7.

Table 7: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of academic achievement of rural and urban secondary school students.

Locality	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Rural N=80	13.43	4.73	2.85*
UrbanN=80	15.35	3.70	

*Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 2.85 is greater than that of the table t- value 1.97 for degree of freedom df (158) at 0.05 level of significance. It is thus concluded that the academic achievement of the urban secondary school students and rural secondary school students are not similar, there is a difference in the level emotional intelligence in respect to locality. The study shows that the academic achievement of urban secondary school students is more than that of the rural secondary

school students. This is mainly because the rural area students do not have better teachers, regular classes, books availability and even the lack of proper infrastructure makes it difficult for the students to perform well in academics. Therefore it can be concluded that the hypothesis is not accepted. There is a significant different in the academic achievement of urban and rural students in their academic achievement. This has been also presented through fig 5.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of the study conducted by Fatum (2008) where the study found that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement of urban elementary school students and rural elementary schools students. The study showed that the urban elementary school students had a better performance in academics than the rural elementary school students.

Figure 5: Academic Achievement of Rural and Urban Secondary School Students

$H_{0.6}$: There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to management.

The results on data analysis of the collected data has been presented in table-8.

Table 8: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of emotional intelligence of private and government secondary school students.

Management	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Private N=80	126.25	14.41	2.96*
Government N=80	118.68	17.66	

* Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 2.96 is greater than that of the table t- value 1.97 for degree of freedom df (158) at 0.05 level of significance. the emotional intelligence of the private secondary school students and government secondary school students are not similar, there is a difference in the level emotional intelligence in respect to administration. The study shows that the private secondary school students' are more emotionally strong than that of the government secondary school students. This is mainly because the government school lack the development of emotional intelligence of students and only focus in the theoretical or bookish knowledge as compared to the private school.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of Sinha&Suman (2013) where the study found that there is a significant difference between private secondary school students and government secondary schools students in respect to emotional intelligence. According to their study the private school students had high emotional intelligence. The finding has been also shown in fig. - 6.

Figure 6:- Emotional Intelligence of Private and Government Secondary School Students

$H_{0.7}$: There is no significant difference between academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to management.

The collected data were analysed to test the above hypothesis and the result has presented in table - 9.

Table 9: Mean, standard deviation and t- value of mean scores of academic achievement of private and government secondary school students.

Management	Mean	Standard deviation	t- value
Private N=80	16.41	3.85	6.68*
Government N=80	12.37	3.79	

* Significant at .05 level

The obtained t- value 6.68 is greater than that of the table t- value 1.97 for degree of freedom df (158) at 0.05 level of significance. The academic achievement of the private secondary school students and government secondary school students are not similar, there is a difference in the level academic achievement in respect to administration. The study shows that the academic achievement of private secondary school students is more than that of the government secondary school students. This is mainly because the government school students do not have better teachers, regular classes, books availability and even the lack of proper infrastructure makes it difficult for the students to perform well in academics.

The findings of this study is similar to the findings of the study conducted by Fatum (2008) where the study found that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement of private elementary school students and government elementary schools students. The study showed that the private elementary school students had a better performance in academics than the government elementary school students. This result has been also shown through fig. 7.

Figure 7:- Academic Achievement of Private and Government Secondary School Students

RESULTS

1. There is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of secondary school boys and girls.
3. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of secondary school boys and girls.
4. There is a significant difference in emotional intelligence of urban and rural secondary school students.
5. There is a significant difference in academic achievement of urban and rural secondary school students.
6. There is a significant difference in emotional intelligence of private and government secondary school students.
7. There is a significant difference in academic achievement of private and government secondary school students.

IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

In India, although the emotional intelligence is not given much emphasis, yet impact can be clearly seen in the academic achievement of the students. It is believed that there is no relationship between the emotional intelligence and academic

achievement but the study shows that there is a positive relationship between the two. Moreover it a myth that the boys are good in academics and even emotionally stronger than girls but the study shows that there is no such difference found between the two. The study has also shown that the government schools lags behind the private schools and have to cover a gap in regards to academic achievement and emotional intelligence of secondary school students. Also, the rural schools in comparison to the urban schools need to meet the pace to reach the level of academic achievement and emotional intelligence. The study also implies that there is a need to incorporate emotional intelligence training in schools for emotional development of the students as there can be seen a strong relationship between the emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students.

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